

Concerted European action on Sustainable Applications of REfractories

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement no.101072625

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Deliverable D3.3 - Report on selected site configurations, process conditions & refractory challenges

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**Funded by
the European Union**

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History of Changes for this Deliverable

Version	Date	Author (Organization)	Inputs / Changes
v 1.00	26/07/2024	Dr. Kinga KLIMA - Tata Steel - Ijmuiden (NL) Dr. Thorsten TONNESEN - RWTH - Aachen (DE)	Template
v 2.0	27/08/2024	Cristian BOHORQUEZ - Montanuniversität Leoben - Leoben (AT) Milena GOMES - RWTH - Aachen (DE)	Version 1
V 3.0	01/09/2024	Cristian BOHORQUEZ - Montanuniversität Leoben - Leoben (AT) Milena GOMES - RWTH - Aachen (DE) Dr. Kinga KLIMA - Tata Steel - IJmuiden (NL) Dr. Thorsten TONNESEN - RWTH - Aachen (DE)	Version 2 with corrections
V 4.0	11/09/2024	Cristian BOHORQUEZ - Montanuniversität Leoben - Leoben (AT) Milena GOMES - RWTH - Aachen (DE) Dr. Kinga KLIMA - Tata Steel - IJmuiden (NL) Dr. Thorsten TONNESEN - RWTH - Aachen (DE)	Version 3 after corrections
V 5.0	20/09/2024	Cristian Bohorquez - Montanuniversität Leoben - Leoben (AT) Milena Gomes - RWTH - Aachen (DE) Dr. Kinga KLIMA - Tata Steel - IJmuiden (NL) Dr. Thorsten TONNESEN - RWTH - Aachen (DE)	Version 4 after corrections
V 6.0	04/10/2024	Prof. Marc HUGER - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Dr Glyn DERRICK - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR)	Formatting, English and final scientific check
V 7.0	17/10/2024	Cristian Bohorquez - Montanuniversität Leoben - Leoben (AT)	Reorganisation and addition of figures
V 8.0	21/10/2024	Dr Glyn DERRICK - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR)	Formatting and English check
V 9.0	25/10/2024	Prof. Marc HUGER - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Dr Glyn DERRICK - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR)	Formatting, English check and final scientific check
V 10.0	30/10/2024	Cristian Bohorquez - Montanuniversität Leoben - Leoben (AT)	Final changes to text associated with Figure 1

Table of contents

1 INTRODUCTION.....	1
2 SELECTED SITE CONFIGURATIONS AND PROCESS CONDITIONS.....	4
2.1 General process challenges conditions in the Direct Reduction.....	4
2.2 Technological innovations to improve the efficiency of hydrogen-based iron reduction.....	6
3 SITE CONFIGURATIONS BASED ON HYDROGEN FLUIDIZED BED REDUCTION PROCESS.....	6
3.1 Circored process.....	6
3.2 Finmet Process.....	7
4 HISARNA PROCESS, AN ALTERNATIVE SITE CONFIGURATION.....	9
4.1 Cyclone Injection Smelting Reactor (CISR).....	9
4.2 Direct reduction and smelting.....	9
4.3 Energy and gas recovery.....	10
4.4 Advantages of the Hisarna process.....	10
4.5 Challenges and considerations.....	10
5 SITE CONFIGURATION BASED ON SHAFT FURNACE REDUCTION PROCESSES.....	11
5.1 MIDREX process.....	11
5.1.1 Advantages of the MIDREX Process.....	12
5.1.2 Challenges and Considerations.....	12
5.1.3 Conditions in the MIDREX process [29].....	12
5.1.3.1 Reduction temperature.....	12
5.1.3.2 Operating pressure.....	12
5.2 Energiron-HYL Process.....	13
5.2.1 Advantages of the Energiron Process [31].....	13
5.2.2 Disadvantages of the Energiron Process [31]:.....	13
6 GENERAL COMPARISON BETWEEN THE ROUTE OF BF-BOF AND DRI-EAF.....	13
7 REFRACTORY LINING CHALLENGES.....	14
7.1 Description of the current scenario of refractories under natural gas atmospheres.....	16
7.2 Refractory challenges in the transition from natural gas to hydrogen.....	18
8 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK.....	19
9 REFERENCES.....	20

1 Introduction

The traditional methods of producing, extracting, and transforming metals used since the Industrial Revolution have remained unchanged, putting the worldwide production of metals at a critical juncture. This situation is particularly problematic in the steel industry, which alone is responsible for producing 2.1 tons of CO₂ per ton of steel [1]. This contributes to the industry's environmental impact, making it a priority to transform steel production processes. This mission has become increasingly important in recent years across the industrialized world.

The classic form of steel production relies on the use of the Blast Furnace - Blast Oxygen Furnace (BF-BOF) route. Here the production of iron is based on the use of the blast furnace as an indispensable tool in the reduction of iron ore. The mixture of iron ore with coke is the basis for the reduction of iron ore, followed by other metallurgical processes such as the blast oxygen furnace to convert the pig iron to steel. This whole process naturally produces large amounts of CO₂, firstly due to the iron reduction process, and secondly due to the need to reduce the excess carbon in the pig iron. An alternative to this process, based on the mixture of iron ore with gaseous phases such as natural gas or in the future, hydrogen, is thus sort. Direct Reduction of Iron (DRI) methods, where the gaseous phase replaces the reducing role of the coke, are thus of great interest. However, only methods based entirely on hydrogen have, at the moment, the desired value of zero for greenhouse gas emissions, which is the overall objective.

The main source of CO₂ emissions in the steel production process is linked to the reduction of ore, primarily carried out in blast furnaces (BF). In this process, significant amounts of coke are consumed, as these materials act as both the reducing agents and structural support for the ore and flux materials during the reduction process. As a result, the primary challenge in the steel industry is finding alternatives to the use carbon as a reducing agent. Several options have been explored, such as hydrogen and mixtures of hydrogen with natural gas. Using hydrogen as a reducing agent is particularly promising because the product of the reduction process is water, making it the most environmentally friendly option. If the hydrogen used in this process is obtained from renewable energy sources, it could lead to a reduction in emissions of more than 80 % [2]. This initiative to reduce part of the CO₂ in the industry is in line with the initiatives of the European Union as shown in Figure 1 [3].

Figure 1 - Projected trend of CO₂ reduction in the European Union. Source: [3].

The reduction of emissions is one of the most ambitious goals in recent years and involves replacing many of the classic processes such as the reduction of iron ore. Currently, a detailed analysis on the transition from natural gas to hydrogen reveals that, starting from a baseline of 453 kg CO₂ per ton of DRI in the natural gas reference case, emissions can be reduced to 40 kg CO₂ per ton of DRI using the DR-H₂ process. This shift enables up to a 91% reduction in direct CO₂ emissions in the DR core process by replacing natural gas with hydrogen [4], [5].

The industrial transformation of iron from the stage of a blast furnace to that of modern direct reduction processes has been a gradual development over the years. The different processes involved are mentioned below and summarized in Figure 2 [6].

1. Classical method from the XVII century: The Blast Furnace Method of Iron manufacturing:

Blast Furnace Operation: This method is the traditional one for the reduction of iron ore into liquid hot metal using coke. This process is very energy intensive and releases high amounts of CO₂ gas as a result of burning of coke in all parts of the process.

2. Early Efforts in the Direct Reduction of Iron ore (20th Century):

Höganäs Process (1918): One of the first methods, used a tunnel furnace for the reduction of fine iron ores with carbon.

Krupp-Renn Process (1930s): A rotary kiln variant in which coal was utilized as a reductant for Iron Ore pellets.

Wiberg Process (1932): A process for iron ore reduction by gas was implemented in Sweden.

3. Industrial Direct Reduction (1950s to 1970s):

HyL Process (1957): The first and only commercially operated gas based direct reduction process with successfully produced sponge iron through natural gas reduction in Mexico which is considered as the beginning of modern gas-based reduction processes.

MIDREX Process (1967): The MIDREX process is a variation of the gas-based shaft furnace where carbon monoxide and hydrogen are used to reduce iron ore. Currently, the MIDREX process is used worldwide in countries like India, Iran, Russia, Saudi Arabia, and Mexico.

Coal-Based Rotary Kilns (SL/RN Process): This technology was created in the 1960s and came to be widely used for direct reduction by using coal as the reductant, especially, in India.

4. Direct Reduction Techniques during 1980s-1990s:

HyL III Process (1980s): Further development and improvement of the HyL process with the addition of shaft furnaces, which are more effective and have higher metallization.

Evolution of the process from 2000s to the present:

Midrex and HyL/Energiron processes: It is these gas-based processes which are still the most economical over modern plants that are capable of producing up to 2.5 million tonnes of Direct Reduced Iron (DRI) in a year. As part of this they are installing hydrogen as a reductant to reduce CO₂ emissions.

Hydrogen based Reduction (Present and the likely future): Innovative processes like the Circored and the HyL-ZR processes are likely to use pure hydrogen as a reductant to reduce carbon in the iron making process.

Figure 2 - Brief picture of the evolution of the iron reduction process.

This report presents an examination of the current site configurations in the transition of the steelmaking industry to a zero emissions industry. Thus, this document seeks to understand how such approaches, like DRI and improvement of fluidized bed reactors, are designed to cut greenhouse gas emissions by improving operational efficiency. A focus will then be made on the commonly used shaft furnace configurations that are used in the MIDREX and Energiron-HYL processes. Finally, this document identifies various challenging aspects in the refractories under transition to hydrogen, in particular with regards to direct reduction in shaft configurations.

2 Selected site configurations and process conditions

Currently, several predominant methods employ reducing gases, such as reformed natural gas or gases derived from the reforming of other processes. In terms of reduction, CO (carbon monoxide) remains the dominant source, and the gradual shift away from CO will depend on the availability of hydrogen, to reduce reliance on CO [7]. One of the primary methods involves using CO gas to reduce hematite pellets in a shaft furnace. This route is expected to remain prevalent until around 2035 when the major steel industries plan to transition to processes that use higher amounts of hydrogen [2]. However, when using reformed natural gas, the reduction process has been observed to be highly uneven, with the upper and lower layers of pellets being reduced to a greater extent than in the middle. This occurs because the reformed gas (CO+H₂) dilutes as it passes through the ore load, decreasing its reduction potential [8]. For this reason, hydrogen is seen as a more efficient reducing agent. However, its current drawback is its limited availability [9].

2.1 General process challenges conditions in the Direct Reduction

It is essential to look at the larger environmental and industrial challenges to evaluate the potential impact of hydrogen-based direct reduction (H-DR) on the steel industry. As one of the largest sources of global carbon emissions, the reliance of steel industry on coal-based methods, particularly the blast furnace process, has come under intense scrutiny. With growing pressure to cut carbon emissions, alternative technologies like H-DR are gaining attention. By using hydrogen instead of coal as the reducing agent in iron ore processing, H-DR offers the promise of significantly reducing emissions, provided that the hydrogen is produced sustainably. However, the technical complexities of H-DR, especially in dealing with impurities like phosphorus, are key to understanding how effective it can be. Phosphorus, a common impurity in iron ore, can negatively affect steel by making it more brittle. Recent research has shown that under H-DR conditions, phosphorus tends to remain in the ore as apatite, a compound that is difficult to remove during this process. This presents a challenge because phosphorus still needs to be dealt with later, typically in the basic oxygen furnace (BOF), where it can be removed more efficiently [10]. This insight into how phosphorus behaves during H-DR is not just a minor technical detail, it has important implications for the widespread adoption of this technology. Another study analysed the energy efficiency of the hydrogen-based fluidized bed reduction process, finding that an H₂ injection ratio of less than 1:3 is optimal for minimizing energy losses, making it critical to improve the performance of specific operational units [11].

Furthermore, the evaluation of particle properties in non-catalytic gas-solid reactions highlighted that the structural properties of pellets, such as grain size and porosity, significantly affect the reduction process efficiency [12]. Finally, a preliminary assessment of the energy and environmental impact of hydrogen-based shaft furnace direct reduction indicated that it is a viable pathway for low-carbon steel production [12].

Hydrogen-based iron reduction presents various technical and economic limitations that must be overcome for large-scale implementation in the steel industry. One of the primary challenges is the complexity of the chemical reactions involved. The direct reduction of Fe_2O_3 to Fe using hydrogen does not occur directly but passes through intermediate stages, such as forming Fe_3O_4 and Fe_{1-x}O , adding complexity to process control. Additionally, at temperatures above $570\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, Fe_3O_4 reduces to Fe_{1-x}O and eventually to iron, while at lower temperatures, Fe_{1-x}O is unstable and converts directly to iron [13].

The Direct Reduced Iron process has numerous difficulties, particularly when it comes to the quality of iron ore, the risk of re-oxidation and the availability of resources. The limited supply of high-grade iron ore and the gradual depletion of fossil fuels only add to these difficulties, making the production process less efficient. A major issue is the re-oxidation of DRI during grinding, which changes the iron's chemical composition and reduces both its metallization ratio and iron recovery efficiency [14]. Additionally, variations in the quality of both iron ore and coal directly affect the reduction reactions, causing compositional heterogeneities in the quality of the final DRI product [15]. Plasma and smelting processing have emerged as a promising techniques for managing lower-grade ores and fines, as it may help improve resource utilization and address some of these challenges [16]. However, the widespread adoption of this technology in industrial settings is still limited, primarily due to high operational costs and the need for further optimization.

Another significant limitation is hydrogen production. The transformation of metallurgy to hydrogen depends heavily on the hydrogen source used. Hydrogen production from electrolysis using renewable electricity can significantly reduce CO_2 emissions, but production based on coal gasification or methane reforming can increase emissions, mitigating the benefits of hydrogen-based reduction [17]. Moreover, process stability and efficiency are affected by the presence of water and the formation of by-products during reduction. For example, experiments of accumulation of Deuterium (D_2) have shown that, in the reaction interface, there is a formation of nanoscale water droplets in the pores, influencing the reduction kinetics and the resulting iron structure [18].

Controlling the formation and distribution of defects and pores in iron oxides is another significant challenge. These defects can act as reaction, nucleation, and diffusion sites, affecting the overall reduction kinetics. The lack of detailed understanding of how these factors interact dynamically during the process limits the ability to optimize HyDR technology fully [9].

Finally, the infrastructure and costs associated with transitioning to hydrogen-based reduction are significant. It requires substantial investments in new equipment and technologies, as well as in the production and supply of clean hydrogen. Without adequate infrastructure and strong financial support, the widespread adoption of this technology may be slow.

2.2 Technological innovations to improve the efficiency of hydrogen-based iron reduction

Technological innovations are essential to overcome the current limitations of hydrogen-based iron reduction and improve its efficiency. Key areas of innovation include [19]:

1. Production of Green Hydrogen:
Increasing hydrogen production capacity through electrolysis is key to reducing CO₂ emissions associated with hydrogen production.
2. Optimization of Reduction Reactors:
Development of reactors that facilitate staged reduction and improve control of temperature and gas distribution, minimizing the formation of by-products and enhancing the quality of reduced iron.
3. Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) Technologies:
Integrating carbon capture and storage technologies for by-products from processes that still use carbon sources improves the overall emissions balance.

3 Site configurations based on hydrogen fluidized bed reduction process

This method uses hydrogen in a fluidized bed for the reduction of iron ore. A recent study showed that a two-stage reduction process (from Fe₂O₃ to FeO, and then from FeO to Fe) is more efficient regarding hydrogen consumption. Energy efficiency and hydrogen usage can be further optimized by improving the performance of specific operational units. The decision to use fluidized bed units depends on various factors, such as the type of ore, the size of the available plant, and the energy consumption required to heat the gas for the reduction [11].

Two methods are widely used and known for reducing iron ore, the transition to hydrogen usage is currently underway. These are the Circored and Finmet processes [20].

3.1 Circored process

The Circored process, Figure 3, is an advanced method of direct iron reduction using fluidized bed technology, notable for its ability to operate with pure hydrogen as the reducing agent [21].

Figure 3 - View of the Circored Process [20].

This process consists of two main stages:

- The first stage is a rapid reduction in a Circulating Fluidized Bed (CFB), where iron ore is pre-reduced to a metallization degree of 70 % at temperatures around 850 °C.
- The second stage involves the material passing to a Bubbling Fluidized Bed (BFB), where the final reduction occurs at temperatures below 650 °C, achieving high degrees of metallization.

What makes the Circored process distinctive is the exclusive use of hydrogen in the reducing gas mixture, which virtually eliminates carbon dioxide emissions. This is possible because hydrogen is produced via steam reforming, a shift reactor and a carbon dioxide removal unit.

This process is promising for sustainable iron production, as it not only allows for the direct use of iron ore fines, thereby avoiding energy-intensive steps such as agglomeration, but also aligns with goals to reduce CO₂ emissions in the steel industry. The only industrial plant to use this process was operational in Trinidad from 1999 to 2006, producing up to 500,000 tons of hot briquetted iron (HBI) per year. Although the plant is no longer in operation, the Circored process remains a viable option for future steel production, especially when combined with technologies that produce green hydrogen [20].

3.2 Finmet Process

The Finmet process is a direct iron reduction method that employs a series of fluidized bed reactors across four stages to gradually reduce iron ore fines. This process is notable for its ability to operate at high pressure and its efficient use of natural gas as an energy source and reducing agent. Material flowing through the reactors is continuous and sequential, beginning with the pre-reduction of iron ore in the first reactor (See

- R4) at a pressure of approximately 12 bar and a temperature of around 550 °C.

Figure 4 - Finmet process schematic [20].

As the material progresses through the subsequent reactors, the temperature gradually increases, reaching about 780 °C in the final reactor (R1), where complete reduction of the ore to metallic iron is achieved [21].

The reducing gas is introduced in a counterflow direction relative to the solid material, enabling efficient gas utilization and high process efficiency. This stepwise approach ensures that the iron ore undergoes various reduction stages: from hematite to magnetite, from magnetite to wüstite, and finally to metallic iron. The exit gas from the last reactor is recycled back to the previous reactors, further optimizing gas consumption. The combination of high pressure and variable temperatures at each stage of the process allows for effective iron ore reduction with lower carbon dioxide emissions than shaft furnace-based direct reduction processes.

The Finmet process emerges as a viable option for producing high-quality iron from iron ore fines, particularly in regions with limited access to high-quality scrap. Its ability to handle large volumes of ore fines, coupled with its focus on efficiently reducing gas, makes it especially appealing in the context of emission reduction and sustainability within the steel industry. The FINMET process has been implemented in locations such as Port Hedland plant in Australia, though challenges were faced during its start-up. Process modifications have since stabilized the operations, meeting production targets for high-quality DRI to apply around the world [22].

4 Hlsarna process, an alternative site configuration

As an alternative site configuration, the Hlsarna process [23], [24] is an innovative iron production technology designed to reduce carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions in steelmaking significantly. Developed by Tata Steel in Ijmuiden, The Netherlands, in collaboration with the ULCOS (Ultra-Low CO₂ Steelmaking) consortium, this technology combines the principles of iron reduction and smelting into a single reactor. This enhances energy efficiency and decreases reliance on traditional raw materials.

Figure 5 - Schematic view of the Hlsarna Process [23].

4.1 Cyclone Injection Smelting Reactor (CISR)

The process begins with a Cyclone Injection Smelting Reactor (CISR), where fine iron ore and pure oxygen are injected at the top of the reactor. Here, the oxygen combines with a portion of the pulverized coal to generate heat, creating a cyclonic combustion zone. This high-temperature environment allows for the rapid smelting of fine iron ore without needing prior aggregation (such as pelletizing or sintering), simplifying the process and reducing costs.

4.2 Direct reduction and smelting

As the molten iron ore descends in the reactor, it encounters an upward flow of hot reducing gas (CO and H₂), produced from the injected coal. This gas reduces molten iron ore to metallic iron. The reduced iron and impurities (slag) are collected at the bottom of the reactor, where they remain molten due to the high temperature.

4.3 Energy and gas recovery

The exhaust gases, rich in CO₂ and CO, can be captured and reused within the process or purified for other industrial applications. Energy recovery from these gases further enhances the energy efficiency of the process [25].

4.4 Advantages of the HIsarna process

- The HIsarna process can reduce CO₂ emissions by approximately 20 % compared to traditional blast furnace methods, and potentially by up to 80 % when combined with carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies [26].
- The process is more energy-efficient by eliminating the need for sintering and separate reduction.
- HIsarna can use lower-grade iron ores and pulverized coal, reducing costs.
- Integrating reduction and smelting into a single reactor minimizes the amount of waste generated during the process.

4.5 Challenges and considerations

- While the HIsarna process has shown promising results in pilot plants, its scalability and large-scale commercialization are still under development.
- Implementing HIsarna technology requires significant investment in infrastructure and adaptation of existing plants.
- Effective carbon capture and storage integration with the HIsarna process is key to achieving the maximum potential for CO₂ emission reduction.

This process investigates the reduction and carbonization of iron concentrate in a CH₄-H₂ gas system, producing Fe₃C. Experimental results demonstrate that Fe₃C can be fully obtained at temperatures above 709 °C, providing a viable pathway for smelting iron concentrate with lower carbon emissions [27].

A smelting reduction furnace incorporating reduction gas composed of electrolytic green hydrogen and circulating furnace gas has also been investigated. This method achieves metallization rates of 85-95 % and significantly reduces carbon consumption per ton of hot metal, achieving CO₂ reductions of over 50 % [28].

5 Site configuration based on shaft furnace reduction processes

Shaft furnace iron reduction is a direct reduction process where iron ore is converted into metallic iron without passing through a liquid phase. This process is conducted in a vertical reactor known as a shaft furnace, where iron ore is fed from the top, and the reducing gas, primarily a mixture of hydrogen and carbon monoxide, is introduced from the bottom. The hot gas rises through the ore bed, causing the reduction of solid-state iron. Due to its porous structure, this method produces directly reduced iron (DRI), also called sponge iron.

The main processes that rely on shaft furnaces are:

1. MIDREX Process

The most widely used direct reduction process globally. It uses reformed natural gas to produce a mixture of hydrogen and carbon monoxide, reducing iron ore to DRI. MIDREX is known for its high efficiency and flexibility in operating with different ore grades and fuels.

2. HYL/Energiron Process

In the same way as MIDREX, this process also uses reformed natural gas but is distinguished by its ability to operate at higher pressures, improving the reduction efficiency and the quality of DRI. Additionally, the HYL process allows the production of hot briquette iron (HBI), which is easier to handle and store.

5.1 MIDREX process

The MIDREX process is a leading technology in producing direct reduced iron (DRI) using natural gas as the primary reducing agent. This method is renowned for its energy efficiency and ability to produce high-quality DRI, making it widely used in the steel industry. Steps involved in the reduction of the MIDREX process are:

1. Natural gas (CH_4) is decomposed in a reformer to produce a mixture of hydrogen (H_2) and carbon monoxide (CO). Reducing gas is essential for the subsequent reduction stage [29].
2. The reducing gas is introduced into a vertical shaft furnace where it interacts with iron ore (in the form of pellets or lumps) loaded at the top of the furnace. As the hot gas rises, it reacts with iron ore, reducing iron oxides (Fe_2O_3) to metallic iron (Fe).
3. The produced direct reduced iron (DRI) falls to the bottom of the furnace where it is collected. This DRI can either be used directly in steelmaking processes in electric arc furnaces (EAF) or briquette for transportation and later use [29].

5.1.1 Advantages of the MIDREX Process

- The process utilizes natural gas, a cleaner and more efficient fuel than coal in traditional blast furnaces.
- It generates lower CO₂ emissions, making it more environmentally friendly.
- The process produces high-purity DRI with low impurity content, improving the steel quality.
- The process can be adapted to utilize different types of iron ore and vary the ratio of reducing gases (hydrogen and CO) according to specific requirements.

5.1.2 Challenges and Considerations

- The economic viability of the process largely depends on the price and availability of natural gas, as well as the problems with the increasing use of hydrogen.
- A significant infrastructure is required to produce and handle the reducing gas.
- The integration of advanced technologies, such as green hydrogen produced by electrolysis using renewable energy, could further enhance the process's sustainability.

The MIDREX process operates under specific temperature and pressure conditions to optimize the reduction of iron ore. These conditions are critical to ensuring the process's efficiency and the quality of the direct reduced iron (DRI) produced.

5.1.3 Conditions in the MIDREX process [29]

5.1.3.1 Reduction temperature

The operating temperature of the reduction furnace in the MIDREX process typically ranges between 800 °C and 950 °C. These high temperatures facilitate the chemical reduction reactions of iron oxide (Fe₂O₃) to metallic iron (Fe) using hydrogen (H₂) and carbon monoxide (CO) as reducing gases. During the process, the reducing gas, heated to these temperatures, reacts with the iron ore to produce DRI with a high degree of metallization.

5.1.3.2 Operating pressure

The MIDREX process operates at relatively low pressures, close to atmospheric pressure, typically in the 1 to 1.5 bar range. Maintaining the pressure slightly above atmospheric levels helps improve the penetration of the reducing gas into the iron ore bed, thereby optimizing the efficiency of the reduction reactions.

5.2 Energiron-HYL Process

The Energiron process [30], [31], also known as HYL, is a direct iron reduction technology that utilizes natural gas as an energy source and a reducing agent. It is one of the most advanced technologies to produce direct reduced iron (DRI), renowned for its efficiency and operational flexibility. This process is conducted in a vertical shaft furnace where iron ore, in the form of pellets or fines, is reduced to metallic iron by a mixture of reducing gases, primarily hydrogen and carbon monoxide.

- The Energiron process operates at temperatures ranging from 800 °C to 1050 °C, depending on the specific characteristics of the iron ore and the reducing gas used.
- A distinguishing feature of the Energiron process is its ability to operate at high pressures, typically between 6 and 8 bars. This enhances the reduction process's efficiency by increasing the density of the reduced gas, which accelerates the reaction rate and improves the quality of the DRI produced.

5.2.1 Advantages of the Energiron Process [31]

- The ability to operate at high pressures and optimized temperatures enables a faster and more complete reduction of iron ore, resulting in DRI with a high metallization level (above 95 %).
- Although the process is primarily designed to use natural gas, it can be adapted to operate with gas mixtures containing different proportions of hydrogen, which is advantageous in transitioning to more sustainable energy sources.
- The Energiron process allows the production of hot briquette iron (HBI), which is denser and more resistant to re-oxidation, facilitating its transport and storage.
- Compared to traditional blast furnaces, the Energiron process generates significantly lower carbon dioxide emissions, as it uses natural gas instead of coke and can integrate CO₂ capture technologies to further reduce emissions.

5.2.2 Disadvantages of the Energiron Process [31]:

- Reliance on natural gas, which can be expensive depending on the region, and the need to operate at high pressures can lead to higher operating costs compared to other direct reduction methods.
- Operating at high pressures and temperatures requires specialized facilities and equipment, which can increase capital and maintenance costs.
- The economic viability of the process is subject to fluctuations in natural gas prices and availability, which can affect its feasibility in certain regions.
- While the Energiron process is efficient, shaft furnaces have a limited capacity compared to blast furnaces, which may not be ideal for large-scale steel production plants.

6 General comparison between the route of BF-BOF and DRI-EAF

Direct Reduction of Iron (DRI) technology is notable for avoiding the typical solid-to-liquid transformation seen in conventional methods (BF). In this process, gas phases, such as reformed natural gas, can be used to reduce iron ore into a solid state, although some impurities remain in the material. This is in contrast to the traditional blast furnace method, where slag is used to remove many

of these impurities. While the gas in DRI generally contains some level of hydrogen, fully transitioning to green hydrogen introduces significant challenges. Additionally, the adoption of DRI requires the use of electric arc furnaces, marking a shift from the conventional combination of blast furnace and basic oxygen furnace. Figure 6 provides a side-by-side comparison of the main characteristics between using blast furnaces and direct reduction processes [32].

Figure 6 - General comparison between the route of BF-BOF and DRI-EAF [32].

Many iron reduction processes already operate with a combination of CO and H₂ levels, like the MIDREX and Energiron processes (Table 1).

Table 1 - Composition of reducing gases in two of the most commonly used iron ore reduction processes [33].

Process	Volume Fraction (%)					
	H ₂	CO	CO ₂	N ₂	H ₂ O	CH ₄
MIDREX	55-58	34-37	1.5-2.5	0.5-1	3-4	0.5-3
Hyl-Energiron	61.8	23.5	3.0	7.1	0.6	4.0

Globally shaft furnace reduction processes are of great interest because the main effects on refractory linings are present in this type of process and most of the iron and steel industry is familiar with or in transition to this technology.

7 Refractory lining challenges

The transition from CO to H₂ does not initially appear to pose a problem since both gases are reducing agents and have been used in combination in reduction reactors. However, it is well known that hydrogen is a much stronger reducing agent for iron ores than CO. This role will likely be similar for refractories; from a thermochemical perspective, both gases are reductants. Thermodynamic calculations have been performed in FactSage 8.1, for an ideal scenario of a high-alumina refractory at the eutectoid point (77.9 % Al₂O₃, 22.1 % SiO₂). Considering this type of refractory in its glassy and crystalline phases, a differentiated interaction is observed with hydrogen and carbon monoxide as is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 - Thermochemical calculations of a hypothetical high alumina refractory in its glass and crystalline phases under CO, H₂, and 2 % H₂O + H₂.

The reduction of aluminosilicates, such as mullite, under a hydrogen and CO atmosphere can be described by chemical equations 1 and 2 [34], [35], [36]:

According to Figure 2 the behaviour of high-alumina refractory differs under different gaseous environments (CO, H₂, and a mixture of 2 % H₂O + H₂) for both glassy and crystalline phases as the temperature increases. The partial pressure of SiO increases with rising temperature across all environments, indicating more SiO is released at higher temperatures. In a CO atmosphere, the crystalline phase produces a lower P_{SiO} compared to the glassy phase, suggesting higher stability and less SiO release at elevated temperatures. One aspect not immediately obvious from Figure 2 is the harmful impact that carbon deposition, particularly in the presence of CO, has on refractory materials. This process can eventually lead to carbon deposition and associated crystal growth, causing volumetric expansion within the refractory material. This expansion induces internal stresses, which can result in cracking and structural degradation over time [37]. A key point in the behaviour of CO, illustrated in Figure 7, is the significant shift in the curve seen at temperatures above 1350 °C. At this point, carbon deposition stops and the environment shifts to being CO-dominant. In a H₂ containing atmosphere, the overall P_{SiO} is higher than in CO, with the crystalline phase still maintaining lower P_{SiO} values than the glassy phase. This demonstrates that the use of H₂ leads to a more reductive environment in comparison with CO. The idea that a H₂ based environment has higher reducing properties than a CO environment is supported by the release of a higher quantity of SiO. An intermediate behaviour is observed in the mixture of 2 % H₂O and H₂, with the crystalline phase consistently showing lower P_{SiO} values than the glassy phase. The influence of mixtures with water has been observed to mitigate the effect of hydrogen reduction [38], [39]. This phenomenon may be encountered in current industrial operations, although areas with reduced or absent water content may exhibit distinct patterns in refractory corrosion. Hence, understanding extreme conditions abundant in hydrogen is crucial as they typify an extreme operational scenario.

A gradual increase in the use of H₂ in energy intensive industries is feasible route to reduce carbon impact. The availability of hydrogen is expected to rise over time, enabling these processes to operate with a higher hydrogen content. Since the Direct Reduced Reactor (DRR) linings are constructed with

refractory materials, this hydrogen increase may result in previously unobserved behaviours or consequences during operation. This has raised concerns among steel and refractory producers, who are keen to identify the problems or new realities emerging where hydrogen will play a significant role in operational considerations.

Until now, direct reduction reactors primarily use fossil fuels, such as pulverized coke or hydrocarbons, to reduce iron ore. Consequently, many of the materials applied in DRR (Direct Reduced Iron) are known for their resistance to carbon degradation. As a result, the application of refractories in these reactors has focused on realising and improving their resistance to carbon, as it is one of the main components known to degrade refractories. However, the new reduction scenario proposes a different reducing environment where hydrogen will play a significant role.

In theory, the use of hydrogen implies the use of a more reducing gas, compared to CO-rich sources, increasing the possibilities of reduction, as shown in Figure 7. In this context, aspects related to the degradation of refractories have gained interest due to the possible consequences of highly reducing environments. However, the reducing environment can be influenced by water, as water is one of the main products of iron reduction with hydrogen. Under these conditions, if there is enough water, it can inhibit the degradation of the refractories to a certain extent [40]. Despite this, due to the many possibilities that may arise in the future where the use of hydrogen is expected to be at the highest possible levels, it is important to consider a scenario where the hydrogen atmosphere is the solely gas phase of the process. Understanding its effect on the phase or molecular changes in refractory materials is necessary.

7.1 Description of the current scenario of refractories under natural gas atmospheres

In shaft furnace reduction processes, the reactors are lined with different refractory materials, each serving distinct functions to withstand the varying reduction conditions. The most well-known process for reducing iron ores is the shaft furnace process, where different refractory linings are employed to endure the harsh reduction conditions. Currently, these reactors face reduction conditions under natural gas, which requires resistance primarily to the reducing action of carbon. The accompanying Figure 8 illustrates the classic design and distribution of some of the refractory linings used in shaft furnace reduction reactors.

Figure 8 - Schematic view of a Shaft DRI reactor with the refractory linings and typical compositions. a) a general view of reactor, b) central zone that exemplified the linings observed in these reactors [41].

The primary refractory linings used in a shaft DRI reactor [31], [42] are detailed below:

1. **Contact Lining:** This lining is designed to withstand contact with the reducing gas and the abrasion of the ore during its transformation. These refractories are typically rich in aluminosilicate materials such as mullite and alumina to endure the mechanical stress caused by creep and abrasion during the process. Additionally, due to the contact with natural gas, they must resist CO bursting, so they are low in iron content to prevent this phenomenon. In hydrogen-rich atmospheres, other issues may arise, such as reducing aluminosilicates due to SiO_2 , which can reduce the refractory's lifespan if H_2 concentrations exceed the presence of H_2O , which could prevent this reduction.
2. **Intermediate Lining:** This typically consists of an aluminosilicate lining that is an intermediate barrier between the contact line and the rest of the reactor. Its primary function is to contain gas diffusion while supporting the overall structure of the reactor.
3. **Combustion Lining:** This lining is designed to withstand the effects of high-temperature gas injection. Due to the sensitivity of this zone, it is usually composed of alumina-rich materials, which are highly resistant to corrosion because of their low reactivity to reduction by CO or H_2 .
4. **Additional Linings:** Similar to blast furnaces, these linings are an integral part of the structure and include various materials such as castables and other refractory components that encompass the reactor's framework.

7.2 Refractory challenges in the transition from natural gas to hydrogen

The transition from natural gas to a hydrogen model shows significant challenges in terms of refractory materials. This change removes the buffering effect natural gas provides, exposing silicon-based materials to conditions for which they were not originally designed. Consequently, this shift necessitates re-evaluating material selection and system design to ensure durability and efficiency in hydrogen-only environments. The consequence of using a hydrogen-rich atmosphere is that the use of existing binder forms of reaction shows sufficient resistance to the reducing power of natural gas; however, in the case of hydrogen, the following challenges arise:

1. The composition of the binder

In the case of using phosphate, various problems can occur due to the reduction of the binder in the form of phosphine gases or the decomposition of this into other forms of phosphorus gas that can affect the reactions taking place in the reactor. In the case of ceramic binders rich in silica, they could be reduced and decompose [43].

2. Other compositional material remains

Constructing a reactor using materials that are inert to reduction, such as corundum, may serve as a viable solution. However, this material has low resistance to thermal shock, so other refractory materials based on aluminosilicates are needed. However, this aspect has different challenges due to the reduction associated with silicon content.

Hydrogen can create reducing conditions that alter the chemical stability of certain oxides in refractory linings. This is particularly critical since, for instance, silica can be reduced under the influence of hydrogen, forming volatile compounds that evaporate and structurally weaken the refractory material. In addition, hydrogen combustion produces water vapor, which interacts with refractory materials and can accelerate their deterioration. Hydration of the ceramic components can facilitate their decomposition and erode the material. Two cases are of interest and can affect the refractory in pure hydrogen atmospheres [38]:

1. Thermal Erosion

Using hydrogen as a fuel or reducing agent can significantly modify temperature profiles within furnaces, implying more severe or more frequent thermal cycling. These thermal changes can cause repeated expansion and contraction of refractory materials, causing thermal fatigue leading to fractures and subsequent material degradation.

2. Changes in Gas Dynamics

Hydrogen possesses high diffusivity and reactivity, which allows it to penetrate deep into the pores of refractory materials. This penetration can facilitate internal corrosive processes not only by the presence of hydrogen itself but also via the by-products of its use, such as water vapor. In addition, the lightness and high reactivity of hydrogen can alter the gas flow dynamics within the furnaces, requiring adjustments in furnace design and operation to minimize the adverse impact on refractory materials.

8 Conclusion and outlook

The transformation of steel production involves numerous challenges, primarily due to the need to shift from carbon-based processes to cleaner alternatives. Hydrogen has become important for sustainable steel production, creating interest in using it as a reducing gas through various processes, which depend on specific factors. Numerous factors influence the decision-making process for selecting a particular configuration for hydrogen-based iron ore reduction plants. One factor is the granulometry of the ore, with shaft furnace methods being preferred for their flexibility in operating diverse particle sizes. Conversely, configurations with access to finely granulated iron ores may benefit from fluidized bed processes. On the other hand, the geographic location of the companies also plays a significant role in configuration selection. For instance, in remote areas, processes like MIDREX or Energiron are favoured due to the easy transport of the briquettes. Conversely, fluidized bed processes prone to oxidation after the reduction are often implemented on-site to avoid re-oxidation problems. These examples illustrate that there is no universal solution for determining the ideal configuration for hydrogen-based iron ore reduction. The final decision is dependent on an in-depth analysis of the specific conditions and needs of each company.

As result the following general views about the site configuration is observed:

- Several processes have been selected to facilitate the transition to hydrogen-based iron production. The choice of process depends on economic conditions and technical decisions based on the type of ore that companies have and the location of the various industries. However, in the European context, shaft reactors are more common due to the large volumes of ore they can process.
- One of the evident challenges is that the transition to hydrogen is linked to the availability of hydrogen. Thus, the supply chain becomes one of the critical factors in increasing the use of hydrogen in ore reduction reactors. In addition, the infrastructure across Europe continues to adapt to create a wide hydrogen distribution network for the companies that require it.
- In the current scenario, the use of refractory materials is based on existing knowledge, so the application of aluminosilicate-rich refractories is still part of reactor design. Due to the long operating periods, the refractories currently in use in reformed natural gas environments must withstand the impact of hydrogen atmosphere as well. This poses some challenges since phenomena that do not occur in carbon-based processes, such as reformed natural gas use, may arise in hydrogen due to the reactivity of this gas with oxides. In this sense, this challenge will significantly impact the research and development of different refractory materials.

This report has presented an overview of some current trends and conditions influencing the transition towards more sustainable iron production methods and their implications for refractory materials. While the processes discussed are well-known, many more innovations will emerge to overcome the challenges associated with the use of hydrogen in iron reduction. The configurations presented here reflect the current state of industry transformation; and, as technology advances, the knowledge documented today will also evolve, leading to more refined adaptations for the use of hydrogen in steel production.

9 References

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